

Fear Of Missing Out As A Moderation In The Association Between Life Satisfaction And The Addiction Of Social Media: Testing A Conceptual Model Among Digital Media Users

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 23, 2021

Accepted:
September 30, 2021

Keywords :

Social Media, Life Satisfaction, Fear Of Missing Out, Compensatory Internet Use Theory

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5542119

Abstract

This study tested a conceptual model positing that a low degree of life satisfaction increases the possibility of addicting on social media while a high level of fear of missing out predicts more addiction of social media. It also aimed to investigate life satisfaction and its link to the addiction of social media and how it is moderated by the fear of missing out. Data for this research were collected from 350 social media users in Saudi Arabia using an online survey. Interestingly, the results showed that a low degree of life satisfaction actually predicted a high level of social media addiction, as did a high level of fear of missing out. These results contribute to the current literature by confirming that fear of missing out moderates the correlation between life satisfaction and social media addiction.

Introduction

Social media today has a significant role in our everyday lives. People can continually check up on their friends' and acquaintances' thoughts and events through these platforms. Social media platforms are also used for information-seeking purposes and for entertainment through games, socializing, messaging, communicating, and sharing content (Allen, Ryan, Gray, McInerney, & Waters, 2014; Liu & Bakici, 2019; Sternberg, Luria, Chandhok, Vickers, Kross, & Sheppes, 2020). Due to the increasing popularity of these platforms, scientists have become curious in understanding the foundations of excessive social media usage, or what could be referred to as "social media addiction." Occasionally named as problematic use of social media or social media overuse (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011; Monacis, De Palo, Griffiths, & Sinatra, 2017), social media addiction involves individuals being very concerned about social media, dedicating a massive amount of time and effort to it in a way that interferes with essential social responsibilities and well-being (Schou-Andreassen & Pallesen, 2014). According to a 2019 survey, forty percent of internet users in the USA aged between 18 and 22 years indicated that they were heavy users of social media. Five percent of participants in that survey stated that this sentence absolutely defined them: "I am addicted to social media" (Clement, 2019).

According to compensatory internet use theory, undesirable life circumstances can increase individuals' motivation to excessively use online platforms in order to lessen negative emotions (Kardefelt-Winther et al., 2017). In this sense, individuals may seek satisfaction and overcome/overlook real-life problems on social media, leading to a high level of utilization of these platforms. However, the literature demonstrates inconsistent results when it comes to life satisfaction and its relationship with social media addiction. While some significant research suggests that generally internet usage and social media platforms particularly correlate with higher life satisfaction (e.g., Morahan-Martin & Schumacher, 2003; Sahin, Erdogan, & Akturk, 2007; Valenzuela, Park, & Kee, 2009; Senol-Durak & Durak, 2011; Grieve, Indian, Witteveen, Tolan, & Marrington, 2013), further investigation indicates that those dissatisfied with their lives suffer from higher levels of online addiction (Flett, Biggs, & Alpass, 1995; Durden, 1997; Caldwell & Mowrer, 1998; Moody, 2001; Meerkerk et al., 2010; Stepanikova et al., 2010; Bozoglan et al., 2013; Kross et al., 2013; Wang, 2013; Chan, 2014). Such inconsistency could be attributed to the fact that most previous studies focused narrowly on the life satisfaction and the problematic desire correlation to use these platforms.

According to Kardefelt-Winther (2014, p. 352), this "direct effects approach has not allowed authors to discover the remarkable predictors of internet addiction, while managing the interrelation with other influencing psychosocial conditions...[and] has not provided a valid reasons for the continued use of internet in spite of its problematic outcomes." Grant, McMahon, Carter, Carleton, Adam, and Chen (2014) add that moderating variables could play a role in this direct link, yet have largely remained unexplored in this area. Przybylski,

Murayama, DeHaan, and Gladwell (2013) argue that fear of missing out or worrying about missing certain information may drive people to excessively check their social media. Although this may be a comparatively newer topic, recent investigation has suggested that being afraid of missing out may intervene between personal characteristics and excessive usage of such platforms (e.g., Beyens, Frison, & Eggermont, 2016; Wolniewicz, Tiarniyu, Weeks, & Elhi, 2018). However, none of these previous studies have investigated whether or not fear of missing out moderates the association between life satisfaction and social media addiction. Thus, in alignment with the theory of compensatory internet use, the current study intended to assess a conceptual model within which a low level of life satisfaction increases the likelihood of social media addiction, and a high degree of fear of missing out predicts a high degree of addiction on social media. Following this investigation, the study explores the function of fear of missing out as a moderator in the correlation between life satisfaction and social media addiction.

Theoretical Background

Social Media Addiction

Internet addiction is an incapability to control one's online usage, which may lead to negative consequences throughout life. Although there are different definitions regarding internet addiction (Shek & Yu, 2012), most refer to a state in which a person cannot control online usage, leading to difficulties functioning (Young, 1999). However, Widyanto and Griffiths (2006) have argued that, instead of looking at internet addiction itself, one should dig deeper and consider specific activities. In other words, individuals are not addicted to the media tool itself; rather, they are addicted to certain conduct online. In line with this proposal, Young (1999) argued that internet addiction can be categorized into five types: computer addiction; information or content overload; compulsions, such as gambling; online sexual addiction; and online relationship addiction.

Addicting on social media seems to fall into the latter category because its primary aim is to establish and maintain connections. Andreassen, Pallesen, and Griffiths (2017) defined this type of addiction as users being preoccupied by social media, using it to decrease their negative feelings. Such users also increasingly use social media for pleasure while suffering distress if they are not allowed to use it. They may forgo their responsibilities and/or harm significant parts of their life and try unsuccessfully to control their usage of social media. In some extreme cases, researchers claim that addiction to social media could be associated with other types of addiction (e.g., Savci & Aysan, 2017; Jasso-Medrano & Lopez-Rosales, 2018; Tunc-Aksan & Akbay, 2019; Chen et al., 2020). Because many Saudis are users of such platforms (Saudi Arabia Social Media Statistics, 2019), this study aimed to measure social media addiction among Saudi users following the Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale created by Andreassen, Torsheim, Brunborg, and Pallesen (2012).

Life Satisfaction

Ginevra et al. (2018) defined life satisfaction as a prejudiced perception of value of life built on the person's decisions and experiences. It may also be defined as individuals' positive affective reactions (Hong & Giannakopoulos, 1994) related to the supremacy of positivity (Deniz & Yilmaz, 2006; Biswas-Diener, Diener, & Tamir, 2004; Veenhoven, 1996). It involves the existence of desirable emotions, the lack of harmful ones, and a cognitive assessment of having a generally satisfactory life. Of course, this assessment varies among individuals because having more positive experiences than negative ones impacts individual evaluations (Biswas-Diener, Diener, & Tamir, 2004). Previous studies have shown that positive estimations of individuals' lives have been linked to well-being, which is defined by Crisp (2001) as "how well a person's life is going for that person" (e.g., Pavot, Diener, Colvin, & Sandvik, 1991; Locker, Clarke & Payne, 2000; Schimmack, Radhakrishnan, Oishi, Dzokoto, & Ahadi, 2002; Gilman & Huebner, 2003; Vemuri & Costanza, 2006; Trzcinski & Holst, 2008). Meanwhile, negative assessments are linked to lower levels of well-being (Wells, Dywan, & Dumas, 2005; Swami et al., 2007; Buelga, Musitu, Murgui, & Pons, 2008; Beutel, Glaesmer, Decker, Fischbeck, & Brähler, 2009; Rustøen, Cooper, & Miaskowski, 2010).

However, these studies have had little to offer when it comes to explaining why dissatisfaction with life can cause addiction on social media. Therefore, this study adopts the compensatory internet use theory, which offers an approach for investigating why a person's life satisfaction might be related to social media addiction. Proposed by Kardefelt-Winther (2014), this theory argues that stressful life events may stimulate individuals to excessively use technological tools as a way to alleviate negative emotions. The theory proposes that people who face negative events in their lives and feel less satisfied may use the internet excessively because it relieves emotional stress. With this in mind, it is important to investigate the reasons for internet consumption when exploring extreme usage. Such examination assists in clarifying the issue underpinning the problem (Kardefelt-Winther, 2015). Based on the assumptions of this theory, this study intended to examine this hypothesis:

H1: life satisfaction's low level predicts a high level of social media addiction.

Fear of Missing Out

Fear of missing out can be described as worried about missing an experience that others might enjoy or as craving interpersonal relations (Przybylski et al., 2013). Social exclusion hinders these attachments, often leading to pain (Lai, Altavilla, Ronconi, & Aceto, 2016). According to Pollard (2012) people experiencing FOMO often persistently acknowledge the activities of others. Beyens, Frison, and Eggermont (2016) proposed that those who have fear of missing out's high levels tend to be obsessed with psychological needs, such as having intimate relationships with others. These individuals are more attracted to social media because it offers interactions and connections with others (Hetz, Dawson, & Cullen, 2015). Recent findings have revealed that when users of social media possess a high level of fear of missing out, they often experience other negative emotions or psychological problems (e.g., Wortham, 2011; Przybylski, Murayama, DeHaan, & Gladwell, 2013; Billieux et al., 2015; Reagle, 2015; Elhai, Levine, Dvorak, & Hall, 2016; Liang, 2017; Hunt, Marx, Lipson, & Young, 2018; McAndrew, 2018; Desai, Chokshi, Chauhan, Gediya, Patel, & Gandhi, 2020; Wolniewicz, Rozgonjuk, & Elhai, 2020). Thus, this study augments this comparatively newer topic through testing the following hypothesis:

H2: Fear of missing out's high level predicts a high level of social media addiction.

As stated previously, the literature also reflects inconsistent results concerning the connection between addicting on social media and life satisfaction. This inconsistency could be attributed to the fact that most previous research investigated the direct association between life satisfaction and the excessive desire to consume such platforms. Grant, McMahon, Carter, Carleton, Adam, and Chen (2014) argue that several unexplored moderating variables might have a part in this direct link. For example, a research led by Chai, Niu, Lian, Chu, Liu, and Sun (2019) asserts that being afraid of missing out moderates the connection between the usage of social platforms and well-being. However, a study by Stumpf (2019) shows that such fear does not actually moderate the contagion of non-work-related tele-pressure experienced within dyads. Continuing this discussion, the current study hypothesizes that fear of missing out will have an effect as a moderator in the connection among social media addiction and life satisfaction. Therefore, this study objectives to test the following hypothesis:

H3: Fear of missing out moderates the relationship between life satisfaction and social media addiction.

Thus, H3 predicts that the greater the magnitude of fear of missing out, the more positive the connection between the addiction on social platforms and life satisfaction. The study expected a negative path coefficient for the interaction term when estimating the moderating effect (fear of missing out x life satisfaction). A negative path coefficient meant that if the respondents experienced a high level of fear of missing out, and their addiction on social platforms was also high, then the outcome was low life satisfaction, as exemplified in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Path model to test the hypotheses.

Methods

Sample and Data Collection

An online survey was administered to assess the levels of addiction on social media, life satisfaction, and fearing of missing out. All constructs of interest were measured with previously used and validated instruments. The survey was created using Google Forms and distributed it across various social media platforms for Saudi users over a period of three months ending in October 2019. Statistics show that Saudi Arabia has 30.25 million internet users, accounting for 90.98% of the population. 25 million (75.19%) of these individuals are active users (Saudi Arabia Social Media Statistics, 2019), making it appropriate to test this model on a sample of Saudis. This choice also reflects convenience sampling because the researcher is Saudi. The sample consisted of $N = 350$ respondents, of which almost a half ($n = 191$, 49.6%) were male. The respondents varied in age from 19 to 54 years ($M = 29.35$, $SD = 8.98$).

All of the item scores collected from the 350 respondents were used to determine the three latent variables (life satisfaction, addiction on social media, and fearing of missing out). A total of 16 missing item scores were replaced using the mean scores for the item. The replacement of a small number of missing values with mean scores is reported not to bias the results of the analysis (Kock, 2014).

Measurements

The current study measured the following variables: life satisfaction, addiction on social media, and fearing of missing out while controlling for the demographic variables of age and gender.

Demographics.

Dichotomous variables were used for gender (Male = 1, Female = 2), and age was measured via respondents' self-reporting.

Social media addiction (SMA).

This variable was assessed by the Bergen Scale of Addiction on Social Media created by Andreassen et al. (2012). This scale measures social media addiction by asking questions about social media habits prompting answers on a five points of Likert scale. This scale ranged from 1 (very rarely) to 5 (very often) when responding to statements like the following: "You are frequently thinking about social media or planning how to use it, you feel a need to increasingly use social media as it helps you forget about personal problems."

Life satisfaction scale (LSS). Diener (1984) indicated that the finest method to measure the life satisfaction variable is by requesting participants to level their satisfaction as a whole, as opposed to tallying up their satisfaction in distinct parts. Thus, the current study measured participants' satisfaction with their life through the Satisfaction with Life Scale constructed by Diener et al. (1985). It consisted of five statements that are measured on a seven points of Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). For instance, it asks the contributors to indicate their opinions about the following statement: "In most methods my life is close to my ideal, my life conditions are excellent, and I am satisfied with my life."

Fear of missing out (FOMO).

The study used FOMO Scale invented by Przybylski et al. (2013). It is a ten-items scale assessing people's level of fear when it comes to missing out on gratifying experiences and actions, through statements like these: "I fear my friends have more rewarding experiences than me, I fear others have more rewarding experiences than me, and I get worried when finding my friends are having fun without me." The survey used a five points of Likert scale varying from 1 (not true at all of me) to 5 (extremely true of me).

The life satisfaction, addiction on social media, and fearing of missing out scales were originally in English, but were translated into Arabic following a translation-back-translation procedure. Two researchers, fluent in both Arabic and English, translated all three scales from English to Arabic independently. They then collaborated to create a suitable version of the translated scales conveying the most accurate meaning. Two other researchers who were also professionals in both languages back-translated the scales without seeing the originals. The researcher compared the back-translation scales with the originals and considered them satisfactorily alike.

Results

Table 1 cross-tabulates respondents' age and gender distribution. The older age group (38 to 54 years) was the largest among male respondents ($n = 94$, 26.9%). In contrast, the largest age group among the female respondents was 19-20 years ($n = 99$, 28.3%). On average, the male respondents were older ($M = 35.88$, $SD = 6.67$) than the female respondents ($M = 21.51$, $SD = 3.38$).

Table 1: Age and Gender Distribution of Respondents (N = 350)

Age (Quartiles)		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
19 to 20 years	<i>N</i>	4	99	103
	% of Total	1.1%	28.3%	29.4%

21 to 27 years	<i>N</i>	14	54	68
	% of Total	4.0%	15.4%	19.4%
28 to 37 years	<i>N</i>	79	4	83
	% of Total	22.6%	1.1%	23.7%
38 to 54 years	<i>N</i>	94	2	96
	% of Total	26.9%	0.6%	27.4%
Total	<i>N</i>	191	159	350
	% of Total	54.6%	45.4%	100.0%

Table 2 presents the tests for normality and reliability as well as the descriptive statistics for the three latent variables (addiction on social media, fearing of missing out, and life satisfaction) that were operationalized through the summation of multiple item scores.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of Latent Variables

Variable	Number of Item Scores	Cronbach's Alpha	M	Mdn	SD	K-S	<i>p</i>
Social Media Addiction	6	.780	2.33	2.17	0.85	0.12	<.001*
Fear of Missing Out	10	.790	4.13	4.31	1.00	0.12	<.001*
Life Satisfaction	5	.846	21.28	23.00	7.12	0.12	<.001*

Note: * Significant deviation from normality ($p < .05$)

The three latent variables were measured for reliability. (Cronbach's alpha = .780 to .846). All of the variables deviated significantly from normality ($p < .05$ for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test statistics). The median scores deviated from the mean scores, indicating skewness in the variables.

To explore the contribution of fearing of missing out as a moderator in the association between life satisfaction and social media addiction, a moderation analysis was carried out using the PROCESS extension for SPSS 25. Addiction on social media was used as the dependent variable, life satisfaction as the predictor, and fear of missing out as the moderator variable. In this analysis, age and gender were considered to be control variables and entered as covariates.

An analysis of standard residuals was conducted, revealing two outlying standardized residuals. The outliers were subsequently removed, and the analysis was repeated with no outliers present (Standard Residual Minimum = -1.724, Standard Residual Maximum = 3.914). Tests used to perceive whether the data assembled the collinearity assumption showed that multicollinearity was not a matter (Life satisfaction tolerance = .161, VIF = 6.211; fear of missing out tolerance = .161, VIF = 6.211). The data confirm the independent errors' assumption (Durbin-Watson value = 2.129). The standardized residuals diagram shows that the data were consists of almost errors that were normally distributed and a normal P-P plot of standardized residuals. Thus, the histogram revealed dots that were not totally on the line, but near to it. The standardized diagram's anticipated values indicate that the data also confirm the homogeneity of variance and linearity assumptions.

The analysis finds life satisfaction to significantly predict social media addiction ($\beta = -.0701$, C.I. (-.12, -.02), $p < .01$). The interaction between life satisfaction and fearing of missing out was found to be significant ($\beta = -.0145$, C.I. (-.02, -.01), $p < .01$). The conditional influence of fearing of missing out on addiction on social media showed corresponding effects at the 16th, 50th, and 84th percentiles (see Figure 2). At low moderation (16th percentile), the fear of missing out rests at 3.0625, and the conditional effect = -.1145 (C.I. (-.12, -.08), $p < .001$). At medium moderation (50th percentile), fear of missing out rests at 4.3125, and the conditional effect = -.1327 (C.I. (-.16, -.11), $p < .001$). At high moderation (84th percentile), fear of missing out is at .50625, and the conditional effect = -.1435 (C.I. (-.17, -.12), $p < .001$). Thus, the results identify fearing of missing out as a positive moderator of the connection between addiction on these platforms and life satisfaction.

Figure 2. Conditional effects of the predictor at 16th, 50th, and 84th percentiles of fearing of missing out.

Discussion

The current study generated a new conceptual model proposing the following: first, a low degree of life satisfaction increases the likelihood of social media addiction; second, a high degree of fearing of missing out predicts a high level of addiction on social media; and third, the relationship between life satisfaction and addiction on social media is moderated by the fear of missing out. The data of the path analysis were consistent with the assumptions of the compensatory internet use theory. In essence, the analysis confirmed that stressful life events (associated with a low level of life satisfaction) may lead some individuals to excessively use technological tools (e.g., social media) as a way of coping. This theory proposes that people who are dissatisfied with everyday life are further expected to be addicted to extreme use of social media because it relieves emotional stress (Kardefelt-Winther, 2014). The current results offer clarification regarding the extreme usage of social media, and in turn, its harmful consequences, without judging such behavior as pathological. Analyzing this relationship also assists in interpreting the problematic consequences of excessive social media usage within the framework of the users' motivation for turning to these platforms and their actual life contexts (Kardefelt-Winther et al., 2017).

The data of this research also confirm that a high degree of fearing of missing out predicts a high level of social media addiction. As stated by Przybylski, Murayama, DeHaan, and Gladwell (2013), users with a high degree of fearing of missing out try to stay continually in touch and updated about others' daily life activities. Thus, it might be argued that these users tend to use social media platforms more excessively. This result allies with earlier research findings indicating that social media users with a high level of fear of missing out tend to experience other negative emotions and/or psychological problems (e.g., Liang, 2017; Hunt, Marx, Lipson, & Young, 2018; McAndrew, 2018; Desai et al., 2020; Wolniewicz, Rozgonjuk, & Elhai, 2020).

The results of the current research also help in bridging the gap in the previous works by confirming that the connection between addiction on social media and life satisfaction is moderated by the fear of missing out. The literature contains inconsistent results concerning the connection between addiction social media and life satisfaction. For instance, several scholars indicate that those dissatisfied with their lives suffer from higher online addiction (e.g., Meerkerk et al., 2010; Stepanikova, Nie, & He, 2010; Kross et al., 2013; Wang, 2013; Chan, 2014). Meanwhile, other studies revealed that internet usage generally or social media platforms particularly correlate with higher life satisfaction (e.g., Valenzuela, Park, & Kee, 2009; Senol-Durak & Durak, 2011; Grieve et al., 2013). Such contradictions could result from the fact that these studies mainly focus on the direct relationship between facing negative situations in real life and turning excessively to the internet due to dissatisfaction. These studies might overlook the moderating role that other variables play in this equation.

According to Kardefelt-Winther (2014, p. 353), ignoring the role of the other variables in such relationships "has been a missing data in most research to date because direct effects models are restrictive by nature and do not allow the researcher to reflect the impact of other variables and therefore masks underlying processes that may be vital in illumination excessive use." Thus, the current study adds to the body of research by revealing that users with different levels of fear of missing out (high vs. low) display varying relationships between life satisfaction and social media addiction. In line with Chai, Niu, Lian, Chu, Liu, and Sun (2019), the results of the current research indicate that individual-difference variables, such as fear of missing out, could play a moderating role when it relates to the usage of such platforms. A potential elucidation for these outcomes is that

being worried about missing an experience that others might enjoy or craving interpersonal relations promotes more social surveillance that could result in social media addiction. In the past, individuals - even when feeling less satisfied with their own life - may not have known that their friends and colleagues were enjoying their lives and doing pleasant activities. The introduction of social media, however, means that such activities are difficult to overlook (Trottier, 2016). Thus, being unhappy about one's own life may cause the user to turn to social media and notice that acquaintances seem to be living "better" lives. They in turn may experience more feelings of missing out, resulting in excessive usage of social media platforms. These findings suggest that individuals facing feelings of missing out could turn to these platforms to balance for their feelings of life dissatisfaction.

Having noted the contribution of the current study and the importance of its findings, it must be emphasized that the current research involved a cross-sectional study conducted among a Saudi sample. Thus, generalizing its results should be done with caution. Based on the current findings, this study recommends that future research examine the same model through longitudinal research. It is also suggested that future studies focus on cross-cultural samples in order to make the results more generalizable. Because this research only included two control variables in its model, age and gender, future studies could include more control variables, such as education level, income, and location (e.g., urban or rural area).

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